

Meaning and Form - an introduction to the Principle of Language

I consider Pure Meaning as the basis of language – meaning, which becomes embodied in form, that is, in structured sequences of acoustic waves. It should be noted that vibrations of the air, that is form, fundamentally differ from meaning in a very precise understanding: there is no way **of deriving any meaning from mere vibrations of the air** or from their representation as graphic symbols (letters, words, sentences) on a sheet of paper. Acoustic waves or their graphic representations are merely *assigned* to meaning so as to evoke it - a generalization of de Saussure's famous statement on the relationship of désignant to désigné (*Basic idea proposed in Jespersen (1925:55) and De Saussure (1931), hinted at in Lyons (1925:134) and Pinker (1994:73), developed in Jenner (1981, 1991, 1993, 2019)*). It was the basic error of Chomsky's so-called Generative Grammar to have missed this essential point.

On the other hand, it is perfectly possible to construct machines that totally ignore meaning. They transform the vibrations of air belonging to some language A into acoustic waves correlated with a language B (or do the same for their respective graphic representations). In the case of basic items like words this transformation is laid down in dictionaries where German 'Baum' is identified with English 'tree', without the dictionary being aware of any meaning. In the case of larger formal units like sentences, translation machines proceed in a similar manner. In many cases, the transformations of larger units like sentences do, however, lead to spurious results. In order to exclude such errors, reference to the linguistic environment is mostly sufficient. This means that a *broader* formal environment determines a *narrower* one, so that such reference mostly produces appropriate translations. As the broader environment still exclusively consists of other formal elements (acoustic waves or their graphic representations), **translation machines may rely exclusively on form** and be highly reliable (which is already true of the most developed among them).

This basic formal procedure was initiated by Distributional Analysis, which has thus made an immense contribution to the pragmatic purpose of translating languages. But translation machines do not further our understanding of language - understanding is therefore quite a different matter. As Distributional Analysis could keep meaning strictly out of its way, it has on the contrary be an obstacle to such understanding. The reason should be perfectly clear. *Meaning represents the very fundament of language.*

Chomsky must have felt the shortcomings of his theory, as he tried to amplify it by means of a concept he called 'deep structure' - opposed to a surface-structure. If the first was to have any sense at all, it should refer to what lies at the bottom of form, namely meaning. But meaning could not be arrived at by purely formal Distributional Analysis, so Chomsky got stuck and soon abandoned Linguistics altogether – and it so happened that after him General Linguistics got stuck as well.

The impasse was obvious, for Chomsky was right and wrong at the same time. Meaning was of no use to the soon flourishing new science of computerized translation, so he could feel assured that he need not bother with it. On the other hand, it was Chomsky's avowed and ultimate aim to explain man's linguistic generativeness – and he was totally wrong when he believed that this goal could be reached without reference to what is the very core of language. In order to lead to a true theory of generativeness, the deep-structure would have to embrace what I call 'Pure Meaning', while the surface-structure would be pure form, that is sequences of acoustic waves (or their graphic representations) described by means of Distributional Analysis.

Let me illustrate this basic point right at the beginning.

First, historically (or phylogenetically): Animals already conceive reality and act accordingly, even if they do not translate these conceptions into auditory or any other signs and signals.

Second, ontogenetically: Infants add auditory signals ('signifiants' or words) only to concepts already present in their mind, otherwise they would pronounce empty sounds. Mere crying is, of course, meaningful too as it usually is the outward expression of pain.

Third, pathologically or 'a contrario': Deaf-mute persons (like Helen Keller) are equipped with 'meaning' independently of its formal realization in sound structures. The fact is proven by their ability to replace sounds with a sign language consisting of gestures.

Fourth, pragmatically through translation: When translating an English sentence into Chinese, I must, first, go back to its meaning before, subsequently, applying the specific rules governing its formal realization in Chinese (as mentioned above, computerized translation-machines proceed without reference to meaning).

And *fifth*, methodologically: The preceding considerations acquire their most general significance as soon as we switch to comparative linguistics. There are but two *tertium comparationis* between any two randomly chosen languages. These lie at the bottom of any specific translation as well as of any general statement about comparative linguistics and linguistic laws. The first tertium comparationis consists in *Pure Meaning* (that is meaning apart from and prior to any realization in form by sounds, letters, gestures etc.). The second tertium comparationis are the *Formal Means* at the disposition of human beings.

Generativeness

What such an approach aims at should be evident: It endeavors to explain, first, the *particular* generativeness of the single speaker of some given language, say English. What is it that enables him to create an infinite set of sentences after having been acquainted with only a finite number of such – mostly when being a child? Second, this approach wants to explain *general* generativeness. What are the necessary conditions and the constraints that govern the human capacity for creating any *natural language whatsoever*, that is those which have already been created and those he may still create in the future?

Somebody has termed my approach 'pragmatic' – a misnomer. Computerized translations that transform a formal sequence of some language A into the formal sequence of some language B deserve such a characterization as they may be put to pragmatic use. The approach expounded in the present article is not useful in this sense. If it has any merits at all, it is its capacity to make us *understand* the true nature of meaning and its relation to form in natural languages. Noam Chomsky had conceived the grandiose idea that a speaker must dispose of a set of specific rules if we want to explain his particular generativeness. Chomsky even hinted to general generativeness when referring to innate ideas at the base of human linguistic capacity. But Chomsky was unable to prove his point. Generative grammar based on distributionalism, that is on a purely formal procedure (like machine translation is by its very method barred from proving what Chomsky wanted to prove.

Syntheses – the basic Units of Meaning

If the preceding assumptions are correct, the first task of comparative linguistics must consist in a definition of Pure Meaning, that is, its units and subunits. Obviously lexical semantic items can only be considered subunits as they fall short of the *requirements of information*. Nobody converses in the following way:

Cold, Peter, volcanoes, serenity, green ...

Hence the real units of Pure Meaning are what I call 'Types of Synthesis', for example the Action-Synthesis /S, a/ or /S₁, S₂, S₃, a/ or the Quality-Synthesis /S, q/ where the first two are made of substances modified by an action while the latter refers to a substance modified by a quality. Only they convey information (In English, these are formally realized in sentences like 'Peter jumps', 'He gives the ball to Mary' or 'The wall is green').

Thus, comparative linguistics starts with the following scheme consisting of three basic parts:

1) Different types of syntheses i.e. those units of meaning that are meant to convey information from speaker to addressee. These are 'formally realized' by means of:

2) definite formal units and subunits (sentences consisting of words etc.) in:

3) structured formal sequences, the most elementary of which we name 'sentences', as these normally represent what in the sphere of meaning are the basic 'Types of Synthesis'.

What I call definite formal units are (a) mono- or polysyllabic sounds, (b) tones, (c) intonation and (d) position.

In natural languages semantic lexical items are for the most part formally realized by mono- or polysyllabic sounds called 'words'. Tones may, however, substantially reduce the number of sound units used for lexical items, as happens for instance in Vietnamese or Chinese.

Intonation is often used to distinguish the functional appearance of a synthesis as assertion or question, assertion or doubt. According to how I pronounce it in German, the Action-Synthesis 'Er kommt' (He is coming) may be understood either as an assertion or a question (S, a) ⇒ /S, a/ or /S, a/?'. The same effect may be produced by means of position, for instance 'Er kommt' (He is coming) versus 'Kommt er?' (Is he coming?) or finally by means of a specific sound particle as in Japanese: 'kuru' versus 'kuru ka?' the first meaning "(he) comes", the second 'does (he) come?'

Syntax versus Paratax

The most basic operation of formal realization does, however, not concern rules of syntax. Much more elementary is the realization of Formal Paratax. It is a characteristic trait of English and other but by no means of all languages that entirely different semantic classes like substances (woman, house, etc.), actions (cry, walk etc.) or qualities (bright, green etc.) may be formally realized in different paratactic classes - which would be normal - but sometimes in the same ones.

'The woman is crying', 'the light is bright' or 'she is happy'

Represent the normal case. The three substances (woman, light, she) are members of the same paratactic class at the beginning of the sentence. Action and qualities (crying, bright, happy) occupy the end. But semantic actions and qualities may fall into the same formal class as semantic substances that in the class of English nouns as in the following examples:

Her (the woman's) crying is hard to bear', 'The brightness dazzles us', 'Happiness makes you feel good'

In other words, entirely different semantic contents like actions and qualities may be formally realized as one and the same paratactic class, the English noun.

Paratax as the way of grouping different semantic classes in formal ones is part and parcel of formal realization – or rather it constitutes its very basis. *And it is specific for each language.* Paratax constitutes the logical counterpart of syntax, as the elements combined in the latter invariably constitute classes. As these paratactic formal classes are language-specific, *there can be no noun, verbs, adjectives etc. as such* but only English, Chinese, Japanese nouns, adjectives, verbs and so on. This is an item of utmost importance when it comes to evaluating the possible performance of Chomsky's Universal Grammar. The latter would only make sense, if the semantic contents grouped in paratactic classes were the same in all human languages. But this is conspicuously untrue. For that reason, Chomsky's Universal Grammar, instead of explaining the variety of languages, explains it away. What is truly common to all languages are the basic elements a) in the *Logical Structure of Meaning* that is substances, action, qualities etc. and b) the basic function in its counterpart: *The Informational Structure of Meaning* that is assertion, question, command; topic/ novum; bound/ free synthesis etc.). These are universals, while formal realization is different for each language. That is the point Noam Chomsky failed to understand.

Hence the natural conclusion that truly comparative linguistics is necessarily made of two different compartments namely 'Analytic Linguistics' and its counterpart 'Constructive Linguistics'.

The first deals with natural languages still in use or found in historical documents. It explains the *particular* generativeness of a speaker of English, Chinese or any other definite language. The second describes *general* generativeness, namely how natural languages are developed by human beings when - obeying to the constraints of formal realization - they create any new idiom.

Analytic Linguistics

Its task is to describe how specific languages like Chinese or English realize Pure Meaning. But as just mentioned, Pure Meaning is not a monolithic entity. It is rather composed of two quite distinct parts, one of which I want to call the '**Logical Structure of Meaning**', while the other represents its informational aspect: the '**Informational structure of Meaning**'. These two taken together constitute the entire structure of meaning.

Let's take the example of a simple Action Synthesis. Like any other synthesis it may appear in quite different informational shapes as question, assertion, command, novum/ topic etc. or as a free or a bound synthesis like in the two English sentences 'Men eat rice' and 'Man eating rice (are usually tall)'. In the first instance, some fictitious man of the moon may just be explaining the eating habits of terrestrials. The speaker provides true information as he supposes to say something new to the listener but in the second sentence 'Man eating rice (are usually tall)' the action synthesis (men, eat) does not contain new information but instead refers to something the speaker assumes to be known by the listener (you know, those men eating ...) The relevant information is provided by the free Quality-Synthesis (they are usually tall).

Meaning is the foundation of language, which form is meant to 'realize', that is to transform in material signs susceptible of being exchanged between the members of a linguistic community. Meaning as such – i.e. mental images formed in the heads of speakers and listeners - is totally distinct from form, just as form – acoustic waves or written letters - is from meaning. An interesting and intriguing aspect of natural languages is to be found in the fact that the formal realization of meaning may proceed in quite different ways. On the one hand, *identical* units of

meaning may be formally realized in *different* ways, while, vice versa, identical formal means may embody more than one meaning. For instance, the above conjunction of two syntheses may be rendered in English in two alternative ways. ‘Men eating rice are usually tall’ or ‘Men, who eat rice, are usually tall’. In Chinese only the first of these formal alternatives is admitted leading to a sequence like ‘Eating rice men usually tall’. This is an instance of different formal realization of identical meaning, in this case the bound synthesis.

The case of one and the same formal pattern expressing more than one meaning is, for instance, to be found in the so-called English ‘relative clause’. The latter may express either an ‘information’ or a ‘non-information synthesis’. Take for instance ‘Peter, who (by the way) is a fantastic young lad, has my special approval’. Though identical in formal appearance to a bound synthesis, we are in fact faced with a parenthesis, that is an information- or free synthesis. The speaker wants to expressly inform the listener that he believes Peter to be a fantastic young man. He could have chosen the more usual formal realization: ‘Peter is a fantastic young man. He has my special approval.’

Constructive Linguistics

Its scope is much more ambitious, though as a matter of fact it does but reproduce on the higher level of scientific theory the mental operations at work in any society where human beings create their own language out of Pure Meaning and Formal Means. Constructive Linguistics wants, first, to describe the field of arbitrariness in natural languages, while, in a further step, it aims at specifying the *limits* to arbitrary variety, that is, the constraints of formal realization.

Taken together, Analytic and Constructive Linguistics cover the entire field of General Linguistics, which I alternatively call ‘General Grammar’ or ‘Semo-Formal Grammar’.

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